

ELEMENTARY SCHOOL ADMINISTRATION MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEM MODEL

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Abstract

Information systems with information technology used can play a very large role in implementing various strategies, such as cost strategies, differentiation strategies, and innovation strategies. The purpose of this research is to develop an information system for administration under the SIMTU application name. This research was conducted at an elementary school in Rokan Hilir District, Indonesia. This research is a research on the development of an information system management model for administration that produces SIMTU applications that can be used by schools in administrative processes. The results of the study show that the SIMTU application is able to help speed up the process of administrative work in schools that are developed according to school needs

Keywords: Administration, Elementary School, SIMTU

INTRODUCTION

Information systems with information technology used can play a very large role in implementing various strategies, such as cost strategies, differentiation strategies, and innovation strategies (Deni, 2013). The current information explosion has a very strong impact on management complexity in general, especially school administration management (Sutabri, 2016). A leader must have the capability to obtain, store, process, retrieve, and present information as material in the decision-making process in the field of school administration that can be morally responsible (Rochaety, 2008).

Administration is an activity related to the management of resources, both physical and non-physical to facilitate various types of services in facilitating operational activities or activities of line organizational units in order to achieve their vision and mission effectively where elements of accountability can be fulfilled.

Mill and Standing ford stated Administration as follows: eight activities of administrative personnel, namely, (1) writing letters, (2) reading, (3) copying (doubling), (4) calculating, (5) checking, (6) sorting (classifying and unifying), (7) storing and indexing and (8) communicating (oral and written) (Amiruddin, 2017). Administrative performance problems according to (Setiawan, 2019) and (Kurniadi, 2016) can occur due to rarely carrying out vision evaluations on a scheduled basis Have never made changes to vision Lack of outreach to students, parents, community, Inadequate infrastructure facilities making it a little difficult for student administrative staff to move more actively to speed up a service, Not thinking about a solution when there is an obstacle.

The results of the initial survey through questionnaires in direct meetings with school principals in Rokan downstream showed that out of 321 elementary school units that were the responsibility of the Rokan Hilir district government, only 24% of the 321 new elementary schools were able to carry out administrative activities properly in the implementation concept. Administrative tasks manually and 76% have not been able to carry out administrative functions properly.

From the field findings, there are: 207 schools that have Administrative Staff with the specifications that there are administrative staff and are able to carry out their duties properly as many as 78 schools, there are administrative staff but are unable to carry out their duties as many as 96 elementary schools and there are administrative staff but are unable to carry out their duties the tasks of 33 elementary schools and 114 schools did not have administrative staff taken over by the school principal.

The results of observations and interviews with SD Negeri 010 Ujung Tanjung, Rokan Hilir Regency stated that currently, the school administration management system at SD Negeri 010 Ujung Tanjung is still done manually, causing paper accumulation, limited data sharing, data inequality and lack of data integrity. The services provided to parents of students are also not optimal due to the possibility of inaccurate data.

It is difficult to make the required reports per desired period, because the manual system cannot generate them quickly and accurately. Therefore it is necessary to implement a management information system aimed at helping facilitate the management of data and information related to schools including new student admissions, academics, report cards and counseling, as well as interactive between schools.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance is a work achievement or the result of a person's work based on the quantity and quality achieved in carrying out its functions in accordance with the responsibilities received. Employee performance is the level at which employees achieve job requirements. A person's performance is a combination of abilities, efforts and opportunities that can be assessed from the results of his work.

Performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization, in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities in order to achieve the goals of the organization concerned legally, not violating the law and in accordance with morals and ethics (Harahap et al., 2022).

Performance Appraisal

Performance appraisal is an evaluation of a person's performance level compared to predetermined performance standards, for consideration in determining promotions, compensation, the need for training or development, or for dismissing someone (Widodo, 2015).

Factors affecting performance, namely 1) Quality and ability of employees. Namely matters relating to education/training, work ethic, work motivation, mental attitude and physical condition of employees; 2) Supporting facilities, namely matters relating to the work environment (work safety, occupational health, production facilities, technology) and matters relating to employee welfare (wages/salaries, social security, job security); 3) Supra facilities, namely matters relating to government policies and industrial management relations (Mangkunegara, 2016).

Employee Performance Measurement

Performance measurement is divided into two groups, namely traditional and contemporary. Traditional performance measurement is carried out by comparing actual performance with budgeted performance or standard costs according to the characteristics of their responsibilities. Contemporary performance measurement uses activity as its foundation (Hansen and Mowen, 2014).

There are 6 criteria for measuring employee performance, namely 1) Quality which is used to measure the ability to produce according to the standards set by the agency; 2) Quantity, to measure the ability to produce according to the amount determined by the agency; 3) Timeless, the extent to which an activity is completed at the desired time; 4) Cost of Effectiveness, the extent to which the optimal level of implementation of human, financial, technological and material resources is used (Rosydi, 2017).

Management Information System

A management information system is an integrated human and machine system to provide information to support operations, management and decision-making processes within an organization (Davis, 2019). Administration management information system from Davis as follows. (1). Integrated system. (2). Computer-based man-machine system. (3). Systems that generate and present information. (4). Systems that support operating functions. (5). Systems that support management and decision-making functions. (6). Systems that require a database. (7). Systems that utilize various planning and decision models (Sinen, 2018).

METHOD

Development research is oriented towards product development, the development process is described as accurately as possible and the final product is evaluated. The development process relates to activities at each stage of development. The final product is evaluated based on the specified product quality aspects.

This research was conducted at the public elementary school level in Rokan Hilir district, Riau, Indonesia. The subjects in this study were Administrative Officers at Public Elementary Schools in the Rokan Hilir district totaling 76 people. The sampling technique in this study was carried out by purposive sampling. The model in this development research is a procedural model, namely a model that is descriptive and outlines the development steps.

Figure 1: Product Development Procedure

Administration Management Information System Application Development (SIMTU)

SIMTU application graphic design, namely 1) Login Menu: Register and Login to the SIMTU application using a Password which is the Secret of the TU Officer; 2) Main Page: initial display of the SIMTU application which consists of several menus such as school profile, Start, Login, File, Data, Process, Letter Print, Template, semester program, attendance and others; 3) School Profile Menu which contains school information such as school name, school address, school location map, vision and mission, statistical numbers, e-mail, Facebook, school website address, and others; 4) The FILE menu contains Institutional Profiles, Access and Exit; 5) The DATA menu contains data on employees, administrators, students, positions, ranks, education, status, family and religion; 6) The PROCESS menu contains a diary; 7) The PRINT LETTER menu contains certificates, power of attorney, promotion proposal letters, assignment letters, statement letters, decrees, invitation letters, transfer/exit letters, letters of misspelled certificates; The TEMPLATE menu contains Minutes of Meetings, Cover Letters, Official Travel Orders, Supervision Sheets for Student Adm Supervision Sheets for Archiving Adm Supervision Sheets for Facility Adm Supervision Sheets, Supervision Sheets for Admin Finance, Supervision Sheets for Admin Staffing, Inventory Card (Kib) A, Division of staff assignments school admin, incoming mail control card, outgoing mail control card, incoming mail agenda book, outgoing mail agenda book.

Figure 2: SIMTU Application Specification

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the calculation of the normality test of administrative performance data for training participants who were taught using the training approach found that all groups had Asymp. Sig. (2 – tailed) = 0.200 and 0.200 for the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Normality Test, respectively. All of these groups have a value greater than the value of $\alpha = 0.05$ so that H0 is accepted which states that the data distribution is normally distributed.

Tests of Normality						
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
TPACK	,133	76	,200	,938	76	,253
KONVENSIONAL	,093	76	.200*	,962	76	,281
*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.						
a. Lilliefors Significance Correction						

Figure 3: Data Normality Test Results for administrative performance of the Training Model

The hypothesis test shows that H0 which states that the administrative performance taught by the school administration management information system model is lower than the administrative performance taught by the conventional training model is rejected.

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
SKOR	Equal variances assumed	2,830	,097	6,214	76	,000	3,000	,565	1,872	4,128
	Equal variances not assumed			6,214	62,237	,000	3,000	,565	1,871	4,129

Figure 4: Hypothesis Test

The school administration management information system model is designed to increase grades, interest, and motivation to study administration in fractional material. This school administration management information system model has been applied to the administration of Rokan Hilir Regency. Based on the results of the trial data analysis, the designed school administration management information system model has been categorized as valid, practical and effective. That way the school administration management information system model can be used in training on classroom administration. By making the school administration management information system model a supporting material, it will help administration. see the administrative understanding of the material in class administration. In addition, the developed school administration management information system model can be used as an example for administration in making a school administration management information system model in other materials. However, before making an administrative management information system model, an administrative school must pay attention to several things.

The practicality of the developed school administration management information system model is known from the trial run. Field trials were carried out after the school administration management information system model was validated by expert and practitioner validators. The practicality test is carried out by administration and administration. Practical data were obtained from the practicality of the school administration management information system model for administration and the practicality of the school administration management information system model for administration. The role of administration in the school administration management information system model is only as a facilitator and organizer, namely only managing administrative learning activities, providing directions so that the material studied is easy to understand and interpret administration. The role of administration as a facilitator is to facilitate and accommodate the diversity of administrative abilities (Agustina, 2018).

Administration has competence in managing training, especially in creating an attractive training atmosphere according to the role it has. Ahmad & Munawir (2018: 21) says that the administrative role is: (1) administrative as a source of learning (2) administrative as a mentor, (3) administrative as a facilitator, (4) administrative as a manager, (5) administration as a demonstrator, (6) administration as a motivator, (7) administration as an evaluator. Based on the description above, it is only natural that the school administration management information system model can improve administrative capabilities in managing training. Training using the school administration management information system model can be used as a reference for the effectiveness of administration.

CONCLUSION

A valid school administration management information system model. Assessment and Responses for Language Experts validator gives a value greater than or equal to 3.214 (≥ 3.0) with a valid category. Assessment and Response to Design Experts The validator gives a value greater than or equal to 3.333 (≥ 3.0) with a valid category. Assessment and Response to Material Experts validator gives a value greater than or equal to 3.412 (≥ 3.0) with a valid category. Assessment and Response to Experts The validator model gives a value greater than or equal to 3.400 (≥ 3.0) with a valid category.

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